

Articles

Representation of the Chinese Indians in three Bengali Detective Fiction

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Abstract

Literary works document the social life of a particular period and they also play an important role in influencing the public opinion. Literature helps the social scientists to understand the attitude of the people towards a particular issue or towards a particular community. This paper examines the representation of the Chinese Indians in some Bengali detective fictions and makes an attempt to understand how the Bengalis view the Chinese residents of Kolkata.

Keywords: Sociology of Literature, Chinese Indian Community, representation

Introduction

Literature is an important area of research for the social scientists. Literary works document the social life of a particular period. They also influence the public opinion. Literature helps to understand the attitude of the people towards a particular issue or towards a particular community. This paper examines the representation of the Chinese Indians in some Bengali detective fictions. It will help us to understand how the Bengalees view the Chinese residents of Kolkata – the diaspora community which has its presence in the city for more than two centuries. This paper is based on three fictions – Kalo Bhramar, Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya, and Dragon Syndicate.

The Chinese immigrants began to arrive in India from late 18th century to explore financial opportunities

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in the country, particularly in Calcutta (now Kolkata), the former capital of British India till 1911 and at present the capital of the state of West Bengal. In the 19th century, a Chinatown developed in Central Calcuttaii. The second Chinatown emerged in Tangra, in the 20th century, located at the Easter periphery of Kolkataiii. This area saw the development of Chinese tanneries. The Chinese population in India began to decline from the time of Sino-Indian War that took place in 1962. The community became an object of suspicion. They began to migrate in large numbers to other countries. Besides the feeling of insecurity and uncomfortable environment, economic reasons too were responsible for their emigration. In 2002, the Supreme Court of India passed an order to shut down the tanneries of Tangra due to environmental pollution. The closure of the tanneries reinforced the trend for outward migration. At present, according to unofficial estimates, the number of Chinese in India lies anywhere between 5,000 and 20,000. Most of them live in Kolkataiv.

Kalo Bhramar

Kalo Bhramar (Black Bee) is a famous series of crime stories featuring Kiriti Roy, one of the well known detective characters of Bengali literature (Gupta 2010)v. There are four volumes of this series and these are written by Nihar Ranjan Gupta (1912-1986). Among the four volumes, the second one is important for us as it refers thrice to Cheenapada – the Chinese neighbourhood (Chinatown) of Central Calcutta. The fiction gives us a picture of the Chinatown during the British rule in India.

In the first reference to the Chinese ghetto, we find two Bengali youths, Subrata and Raju, passing through the Chinese locality. These two friends are facing threats from a gang headed by an unknown dangerous criminal. Subrata's cousin was kidnapped and there was no trace of him. When they are walking through the Chinatown, Raju feels that somebody is following them. He had a criminal background in the past and from his experience he suspects the man to be a Burmese.

Next day, the two men approach the private detective Kiriti Roy for help. The detective begins his investigation and suspects that a gang is operating from Chinatown. He plans an operation, asks Subrata to be a part of it and asks the latter to wait in Bentink Street where dozens of Chinese shoe shops are located.

In the Chinatown, Kiriti traces the house which is the den of the gang. The house is guarded by an 'ugly looking' old Chinese lady and a half-asleep Chinese youth. The Bengali detective overpowers both of them in quick time.

Then he reaches the room where the cousin of his client is held hostage. Other than the captive, three criminals are present in the room, including the gang leader. Soon a fight breaks out between Kiriti and the criminals and ultimately, Kiriti gets injured but he somehow manages to escape. But, he fails to free the kidnapped person. There is no mention of the ethnic identity of the criminals. However, the gang leader is shown as capable of speaking both Bengali and Chinese.

Kiriti again ventures into the area with the police to conduct a raid on the criminal den. He, along with Subrata, reaches a shop named Hong Kong Shoe Factory at 10 a.m.

Two police constables are kept waiting outside the shop. In front of the shop, a half-asleep middle aged Chinese is seen smoking a pipe. He gets awoken by their arrival and he welcomes them by saying, 'Juti Saab, achhi juti' (Gupta, 2010, p. 124).

The private investigator and his companions carry out a search in all the rooms of the building. Kiriti finds an ugly old Chinese woman in the next room. She was sleeping; covering her body with an old dirty wrapper (chador).The old woman awakes, recognizes Kiriti and starts uttering something in Chinese. Without bothering about her, the detective and others move towards another room. A foul smelling jute curtain, is hanging in front of the door. Kiriti removes the curtain and sees three Chinese women engaged in household activities. One of them is cooking food in an oven, another is slicing vegetables with a knife and keeping them in a

broken container (sanki).The third woman is sitting on a cane-made-tool (mora) and sewing a costume. These women are surprised by the sudden arrival of the unknown men. All three get up. In this shop, a young woman is seen as slicing leather with scissors. A Chinese youth is found sewing something while sitting on a machine. Both of them raise their heads, watch the visitors for a moment and again concentrate on their work. The middle-aged Chinese shop keeper politely enquires, in highly accented Bengali, 'Ki juti chai babu?' (Sir, what kind of shoes are you looking for?) (Gupta, 2010, p. 124). To this, Kiriti replies that they want to search the shop. A few Chinese youths try to resist. One of them brings out a sharp knife to threaten Kiriti. The detective overpowers him within a flash and blows a whistle. Two police constables, who are waiting outside, enter into the shop. The body language of Chinese men changes all of a sudden. They do not create any more troubles for the detective. The search is completed without any positive result. The detective becomes a little disappointed for not finding the gang or the captive. He, along with all his companions, leaves the Chinese shoe shop and the Chinatown.

From a reading of this novel, the following conclusions can be made about the representation of the Chinese and Chinatowns.

Firstly, there is no significant Chinese character in this story. In fact, no Chinese has been mentioned by his or her name here. There exists a very brief mention of the Chinatown in the entire novel. The place has been described as a safe haven for the criminals. The Chinese provide protection to the gang members in their dark locality. The author has given a description of the place to create a mysterious environment. So, it can be said that Chinatown has been used to add colour to this entire crime story. The representation of the Chinese ghetto reinforces the conventional mainstream idea of the locale being dark, mysterious and a site associated with criminal activities. The overall environment offers a picture of shabbiness and of mysterious otherness. The dingy background as portrayed by Nihar Ranjan Gupta suits the overall scheme of a detective story that deliberately seeks sites where plans of dark crimes are

born and nurtured. However, though the Chinatown has been represented in a negative light, the Chinese characters are not the main villains in the story. In fact, they are not even the member of the dreaded gang. They only help the criminals to take shelter in their dark locality which is not easily accessible to the police. Moreover, the Chinese goons are portrayed as neither skilled nor very clever. The Bengali detective overpowers them again and again without much difficulty.

Secondly, this literary work shows that the Chinese are very professional; they manufacture shoes with utmost attention and politely behave with their customers. But the same people become ferocious when somebody shows too much curiosity and interferes in their affairs. However, they fear the police and avoid getting involved in any sort of trouble with the law enforcement agency.

Thirdly, the descriptions of their buildings (dark rooms), their articles (broken container, foul smelling curtain) and items of everyday use (old dirty wrapper) give an impression that the Chinese shoe makers belong to the low income group of the society.

Fourthly, more than once, the Chinese characters have been described as half-asleep. Perhaps the intention is to suggest that they are addicted to opium though that has not been clearly mentioned.

Fifthly, the novel throws some light on the language used by the Chinese. The old Chinese woman speaks Chinese (the author describes it as kichir michir with a sense of ridicule) and the middle aged male Chinese shopkeeper speaks accented Bengali with his customers. This is understandable because the women have lesser chance to interact with the local people compared to that of the men. However, the Chinese youth speaks English clearly. Perhaps, it indicates the change of generational attitude, change in their preference for education and for language.

Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya

Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya (mystery surrounding Jhao Jhien's murder) (2007) is a detective novel, written for the children by a well-known female writer Suchitra Bhattacharya (Bhattacharyya, 2007).

In this novel, Liang, a Chinese school boy, approaches a Bengali girl of the same age so that she can introduce him to a lady detective, who happens to be the aunt of the girl. The objective of the Chinese is to solve the mysterious death of his uncle Jhao Jhien. The girl named Tupur, who often assists her aunt to solve mysterious cases, records some preliminary information and the search for truth starts. The detective and her associates visit various places including the Jhien's residence in the Chinese neighbourhood of central Calcutta and a Chinese school where Jhien served as a teacher. Jhien, aged about fifty years, was a brilliant student in his early days and after completing his M.A. in history from the Calcutta University, he was carrying out a research very seriously not for the sake of a Ph.D degree but to unravel an unknown chapter of China's past. One day, he purchased an antique item from a curio shop and soon after, he was found dead on the road in a relatively quiet place near the River Ganga.

Initially, it seems to be a case of fatal road accident. Later, the investigation reveals that the item was a historically valuable map, which might change our knowledge of the history of China as disseminated through the writings of western scholars. It is further revealed that in order to grab the highly valued item and to take the credit of making a great discovery, Jhao Jhien was murdered by a professor of History, who is a Bengali and who belongs to Hindu upper caste.

The novel shows the tendency among the Bengalis to associate the Chinese with mystery. When Tupur tries to contact her detective aunt Mitin over telephone to inform the latter about a new murder case, the call is received by Mitin's husband Partha, who remarks, "Oh God! A case involving a Chinaman! It must be very mysterious". (Bhattacharyya, 2007:13)

Although it is a detective novel and is about a murder mystery, the author tries to counter the popular Bengalee notion about the Chinese – the Chinese are mysterious people. We find, Tupur's father Abani saying, "So what if a case comes from the Chinamen? Are they murderers or rogues?" (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 20). This literary work repeatedly cautions the readers about making any kind of sweeping generalization about the Chinese. The novel not only questions the stereotyping of the Chinese but also brings out the reasons that are responsible for the formation of negative attitude towards the Chinese diaspora.

Abani explains to his daughter:

We do not care to know their rituals, life style (adob kayda), festivals, ceremonies etc. The ignorance leads to concerns, mystery and fear (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 21) (translated by the author).

The novel shows that direct contact between the Bengalis and the Chinese community still remains quite minimum, basically confined to the client-businessman/ service provider relationship or friendship in the schools. The Chinese on their part have not adequately adopted the language and culture amidst which they live. Liang cannot pronounce Tupur's 'good name' 'Aindrila'. In fact, he fails to utter 'Tupur' properly (ibid: 10). Lian's Bengali is mixed with English words and it is heavily accented.

Bhattacharya has done some research about the community. Internet sources have been tapped for the purpose as we see some characters in the novel like Abani, young assistants father, and Partho, female detective's husband collect information regarding the community (history of arrival, settlement, population, Chinatowns, social rites etc.) which are fed to the investigation team. The knowledge about the community remains largely confined to a miniscule section of the scholars and this never percolates into the Bengali neighbours in a big way.

There is evidently a lack of knowledge related to the Chinese in Kolkata. There is very little socio-cultural interaction between the Bengalees and the Chinese – Bhattacharya as an author seems to have fallen back on the internet sources which has become a valuable and indispensable source for such little known areas. Bhattacharya skillfully and effectively integrates the internet sources into the novel.

The author has made attempts to familiarize the readers with the Chinese customs, culture and history. The readers are informed that for the Chinese, the family name precedes the first name (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 15). Shanghai is located in northern China and people from that region prefer little bit more boiled food (ibid:34). The Chinese consider brinjal harmful for health (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 78). There is a mention about the rituals related to death. When a close relative dies, women tie blue wools to their heads and men wear black tapes in their hands. These items are burnt after forty-nine days from the day of demise (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 37). The Chinese preserve the dead body for two to three days before the burial, until, they believe, the spirit sees its reflection in the water of the Huang Ho River and becomes convinced of its death. The novel also provides information about Chinese Calendar (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 113), Moon Festival (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 114), Lantern Festival (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 114) and different Chinese rituals (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 114).

The novel contains some information about the Chinese diaspora in Kolkata. The figure of the Chinese population in the city is mentioned as twenty thousands (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 45)vi. There is a mention of the first Chinese colony on the Indian soil which came up in the late eighteenth century at Budge Budge, near Kolkata (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 77). The novel also presents the current state of that place named Chinamantala in Achipur, named after the first settler Tong Atchew (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 101). The Chinese in Kolkata are engaged in different occupations depending on the region in China their ancestors had come from (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 32). The women too participate in economic activities. Liang's mother looks

after the laundry shop, during noon, when her husband comes home for lunch (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 31). There are two Chinese newspapers that are published from Kolkata (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 38). There is also a description of the long, serpentine, dark Chattawallah Gully, a well known lane in Central Kolkata's old Chinatown (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 32)

There is also a description of the drawing room of the Zhao family:

There is a colourful showy lampshade. The doors and the windows are covered with curtains made of silk. Two large framed pictures are visible on the wall. Perhaps, one of them is a reproduction of a picture made by a famous artist. The other belongs to San Yat Sen. There are Chinese dolls and flower-vase in the showcase beside Barbie doll. Small soft toys are placed over the television. One brass made wind chime is hanging in the room. It is swinging in the wind generated by the electric fan and making sounds. (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 33)(translated by the author)

The way the room has been decorated, reflects the intention of the Zhao family to maintain their 'Chinese' identity. There are more evidence to substantiate the argument. Liang's father speaks Chinese at home with his daughter. They celebrate the traditional Chinese moon festival. They follow the Chinese rituals (Bhattacharyya, 2007, pp. 17-37). Zhao, the researcher who was murdered, wanted to counter the 'wrong' pictures given by the European historians about the history of China, the land of Zhao's ancestors. Mrs. Yuan, Principal of the Nanking High School still feels proud of Chinese language (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 86). Running a Chinese school, though not very successfully and publishing Chinese newspapers, show the desire of the Chinese diasporic people to preserve their traditional culture.

The novel also captures the changes in the social life of Kolkata's Chinese Diaspora. It refers to the

gradual disappearance of the old Chinatown. Most of the Chinese have left the area and have shifted to Tangra, the second and the relatively newer Chinatown in Eastern Kolkata (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 88). However, no description of Tangra has been provided in the novel. There is also mention of the change in their culture. Mrs. Yuan, Principal of the Nanking High School, lamented that the Chinese parents' loss of interest in sending their children to a Chinese school. Instead, they prefer the English medium schools for practical reasons. Mrs. Yuan admits the rationale for such inclination – one cannot find a job without knowledge of the English language (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 86). The novel says that the crisis of language is a problem for all other non-English speaking communities: all the mother tongues, except English, are facing the problem of lack of patronage. (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 86). The shift in attitude is also found among the members of the new generation as well. Liang does not wish to run the family laundry business; he wishes to be a teacher in future (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 32).

Dragon Syndicate

Another Bengali detective fiction featuring the Chinese of Calcutta is Dragon Syndicate (2013) by Subhas Dhar (Dhar, 2013). The fiction is included in a volume, with two other fictions, which are also named Dragon Syndicate. The exact year of the writing of the story is not known. In the 'Introduction', the author informs the readers that all the three stories in the volume (the other two being "Duplicate Key" and "Atanker Tila" or "The Hillock of Terror") are written between 1960 – 1975.

The title story, Dragon Syndicate is the story of an investigation conducted by two police sleuths Sushanta and his companion (Satyen Ghosh). In this fiction, the plot revolves round the characters of a Chinese goon (Wang Fu) and his mentor (a Chinese middle-aged woman named Elaine Yap). These Chinese characters are engaged in anti-social activities like

gambling (Mah-Jong), business in drug-dens, goon-agency (with headquarters in Dragon Syndicate located in Topsia), cheating and snatching and so on.

One day, Mr. Nishikanta Bhatta, a Professor of Philosophy, is attacked by two goons on the street. He lodges a complaint with the Park Street Police Station and the probe begins. The two sleuths visit two Chinatowns of Kolkata and contact some Chinese residents of the city. One of those residents is Dr. Hu, a Chinese dentist.

Sushanta soon discovers that it is the work of Wang Fu, a notorious criminal and an escaped prisoner. He is chameleon-like, changes his identity, at will. Wang Fu is a Chinese (of Chinese and Nepali parentage) but is also known as Chao, John and as Tamang. Further investigation and much adventure reveal that Wang Fu is now running a syndicate which lends rowdies to parties interested in taming their opponents. The gang is also involved in other petty and organised crimes. Elaine Yap who herself is in charge of a drug-den is also the kingpin and owner of the Syndicate. The gang adopts different measures to intimidate the police. On one occasion, Wang Fu impersonates as woman and escapes. But in the end, all the culprits are arrested and the order is restored.

The story offers a brief description of the localities where the Chinese are living for more than a century. It also gives an idea of the social life of the Chinese Indians in Calcutta. Ghosh, for instance, gives a true picture of the Chinese presence in Calcutta, "Boss, once the Chinese had their heydays in this city. They crowded places like Tangra, Mission Road, Bowbazar and Bentink Street. These Chinese were well-known because of their professional skill in shoe-making, restaurant, carpentry etc." (Dhar, 2013, p. 15) However, it also confirms and reinforces the stereotypes prevalent among the residents of Calcutta. These mainly concern the image of the Chinese Indians as being remote and mysterious, from linguistic and cultural points of view. It has been mentioned, "The residents of the Chinese locality prefer living in an environment of light and shade" (Dhar, 2013, p. 19)(translation by the

author). The Chinese are described as impassive and inscrutable – they are 'yellow' (an overt signifier of 'otherness') (Dhar, 2013, p. 20), indistinguishable ("All Chinaman are cast in the same mould". (Dhar, 2013, p. 20). The Chinese are also mentioned as a well-knit community. Sushanta, the detective observes, "The Chinese are indeed very much organized. Each member is well-informed of the others. But nobody will open his mouth if one of their own is involved." (Dhar, 2013, p. 20) The Chinese are also shown as an insular community. They are the 'others' – men and women who are different from the Indians living in Kolkata. In the entire story the Chinese characters are seen as 'others', they belong to a world which, though in proximity with the mainstream Indians, appear to be distant. The difference between the two worlds is often bridged by occasional visits of a dentist (Dr. Hu) or the law-enforcers' invasion into the Chinese worlds of the Wang Fuses and Elaine Yaps. There are also some indications of limited interactions with the local population they contact and involved the locals and the professionals outside the community. For example, Sushil Moktar is their lawyer and the local rowdies are, for instance part of the Dragon Syndicate gang. The fiction also mentions the establishment of a temple, dedicated to the Hindu Goddess Kali, by the Chinese in the Chinatown of Tangra.

In this story, the emphatic images of the Chinese Indians are that they are either comical or criminal or both. They are impassive, and are inscrutable, linguistically, culturally. They appear to be comical for their ethnic looks, and their pronunciation of the Indian languages. The way they behave arises in the Bengali onlookers a sense of laughter, derision and even awe. The dentist Dr. Hu, for instance, is ever-smiling, (Dhar, 2013, p. 16). His pronunciation of Bengali words creates a comic effect. Wang Fu, on the other hand, generates awe by reason of his sheer strength, cunning, ingenuity and propensity to criminal activities. Elaine Yap, the king-pin (or queen-pin) of the gang, is scheming, aggressive, and a good organizer of criminal groups.

Conclusion

As far as the theme, the plot and the style of the representations are concerned, all the literary works analyzed in this paper differ from one another. However, despite diversities, they share several common features.

Firstly, all the three fictions have tried to give a description of the Chinese localities in Kolkata. But only Dragon Syndicate provides the readers with the description of two Chinatowns of Kolkata – one located in Bowbazar, close to the centre of the city and another in Tangra, located in the eastern periphery of Kolkata. The other two literary works focus only on the Chinatown in Central Kolkata.

In Kalo Bhramar, compared to the other two fictions, a detailed description of the Chinatown during the British rule is given. Though the lane of the Chinatown is not too narrow, it is extremely dark. Nothing is visible in darkness, not even a person standing beside another. On both sides, the walls of the building have risen straight from the lane. Some rays of light come out of a window located at a height of about ten feet. The bad odour of rotten fish and leather make the atmosphere suffocating (Gupta, 2010, p. 114). The novelist also offers a brief description of a Chinese shoe- factory-cum shop. These units are attached to their residence. The shop is not very large in size. There is a platform surrounded by a wooden railing. At one side of the room, there is a heap of leather. In the opposite side, there stands a wooden staircase to reach the above floor (Gupta, 2010, p. 124). We also find a description of the rooms where the Chinese shoe makers live. Most of the rooms are quite dark even at day time. In one of the rooms they find piles of paper- made shoe-boxes. There is a machine to sew leather. They also see a wall lamp, not cleaned for days, hanging from above (Gupta, 2010, p. 126). The description of the Chinatown in Kalo Bhramar helps the readers to form some idea of the life of the Chinese settlers in Kolkata.

Similarly, Dragon Syndicate mentions several aspects related to the life of the Chinese community in Kolkata: the occupational preference of the community, their main festival – the Chinese New Year, the difficulties the community faced during the Sino-Indian war which resulted in massive out-migration etc.

But these two literary works, unlike Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya, do not bear the sign of extensive research works on the lives of the Chinese diaspora in India. Bhattacharya has the objective of creating awareness about the history and the culture of the Chinese diaspora. Her novel provides the history of the Chinese colony at Budge Budge. In fact, the story reached its climax in the place where the first Chinese settlement had appeared. This novel, like the other two, informs the reader of some basic information about the Chinese diaspora, such as – their occupational pattern, language, region from where their ancestors had arrived in India, Chinese festivals, Chinese Calendar, rituals they perform etc.

Unlike Kalo Bhramar or Dragon Syndicate, Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya presents the Chinese as a calm, peace-loving people. Liang's father remarked:

We are not at all concerned about those maps and history. Jhien was an exception. We, the Chinese living here, remain busy in earning a living, in getting a job or in running a business (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 89).(translated by the author)

Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya glorifies the Chinese diasporic community in several ways. The main Chinese character, Jhao Jhien, is shown as a brilliant student, a very competent historian who dedicates his life for unraveling some unknown facts in China's history. Jhao's colleagues, the Chinese teachers of a primary school are shown as very kind-hearted, very polite persons. The family of Jhao's brother has been praised

for their sober behaviour and for the hospitality they had shown to their Bengali guests.

The novel praises the Chinese as the oldest civilized race of the world (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 20). Several contributions made by the Chinese to the world civilization have been mentioned e.g. tea, paper, printing technique etc. (Bhattacharyya, 2007, pp. 21,34). The novel shows some efforts, on the part of both the Chinese and the Bengalis, to close the gap that exists between the two communities. Liang approaching Tupur to solve the mystery of his uncle's death is a good example. His uncle, Jhien, approaches some Bengalee historians to discuss his area of interest. Liang feeds his classmates cake on the occasion of the Chinese Moon festival (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 17). His mother receives his friends with tasty authentic Chinese food (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 86) .

The important point is that Jhao Jhien Hatya Rahasya – call upon the readers to close the mental distance between the Indians and people who came from China. It laments the lack of knowledge on the part of the Bengalees about their Chinese neighbours .The two comments quoted below demonstrate the novelist's disapproval of the Indian attitude towards the Chinese Indians:

So many Chinese are living in Kolkata, not for a few days but since the time of Warren Hastings. Yet, we need to surf the Internet to know about these people (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 114) .

Really, we the Bengalis are too much self-centered. We are required to open the window of our mind more (Bhattacharyya, 2007, p. 114) .(translated by the author)

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Notes

¹The Chinese community in India comprises immigrants and their descendants. The community is referred to as Chinese Indians or Indian Chinese. In this paper the term "Chinese Indians" has been used because it indicates that they are one particular kind of Indians.

2 Tong Atchew, a sailor, was the first Chinese settler in Calcutta. He arrived in the city sometime in the 1770s. He set up a sugar factory near Budge Budge, thirty three kilometer from Calcutta for which he brought workers from China. Atchew's commercial enterprise ultimately failed a few years later. But it effectively started the process of Chinese influx. The sugar factory was put up for auction in 1803. The Chinese labourers left the place and moved to Calcutta. Gradually, the numbers of Chinese in Kolkata began to increase. A Chinatown developed in Central Calcutta.

3 After their arrival in India, the Chinese found it convenient to engage themselves in some professions which were usually considered to be 'polluting' by the upper caste Hindu residents. They gradually entered into such 'lowly' professions like laundry, restaurant, carpentry, tanning and so on. In the beginning of the 20th Century, a few Chinese shoe-makers decided to take up tanning and established their units in Tangra.

4 Those who are interested to know more about the history of the Chinese Indians may see the writings of Banerjee 2007; Barret 2004; Chatterjee 2005; Halder 2007; Li 2006; Liang 2007; Sen Gupta 1979; Sen 2007; Sreepantha1999; Zhang 2009 etc. Those who are interested in the social life of the Chinese Indians may see the writings of Ali 1982; Banerjee, et al 2009; Goradia 1972; Oxfeld 2007; Roy 2008.

5. The complete volume of Kalo Bhramor, comprising four volume, does not mention the publication year of the particular part that I have discussed in this paper.

6 The first edition of the book came out in 2007. This figure of the Chinese population in the city is debatable.